

EXPRESSION OF FASCIN IN HODGKIN LYMPHOMA

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Abstract

Objective:

To determine the frequency of expression of fascin in Hodgkin lymphoma in the Pakistani population.

Study design:

Cross-sectional descriptive study

Place and duration:

Diagnostic & Research Laboratory of LUMHS, Jamshoro, for a duration of 6 months i.e. from Nov/2023 till April/2024.

Patients and methods:

After obtaining written informed consent, 65 patients who met the selection criteria were enrolled. Routinely processed formalin- or B5-fixed, paraffin-embedded tissue specimens were retrieved from the Diagnostic & Research Laboratory of LUMH, the diagnosis of Hodgkin lymphoma (HL) was made and expression of fascin was assessed as per standard procedure. The findings were noted down and were subjected to statistical analysis.

Results:

The median (IQR) age of the patients was 35 (9.5) years. The median (IQR) duration of symptoms was 7 (3.5) months. There were 42 (64.6%) males and 23 (35.4%) females. The commonest type of HL was nodular sclerosis HL i.e. in 49 (75.4%) patients, followed by mixed cellularity HL in 12 (18.5%) patients. In terms of stage of HL, stage I was present in 18 (27.7%) patients, stage II was present in 25 (38.5%) patients, stage III was seen in 18 (27.7%) patients and stage IV was present in 4 (6.2%) patients. Expression of fascin occurred in 35 (53.8%) patients of HL.

Conclusion:

In patients with Hodgkin lymphoma, *fascin* was expressed in 38.5% patients.

INTRODUCTION:

The 55-kd monomeric globular actin-bundling protein known as fascin was first identified in sea urchin egg cytoplasmic extracts. It facilitates the bundle formation of F-actin molecules [1]. The development of dendritic processes and the function of dendritic system cells, which are involved in lymphocyte homing and migration as well as antigen presentation, depend on globular actin-bundling proteins [2]. A monoclonal antibody to fascin has been shown in immunohistochemical tests to specifically identify dendritic cells in three lymphoid organs. Prior research has demonstrated that reactive follicular hyperplasia and follicular lymphoma neoplastic follicles exhibit altered fascin expression in germinal center dendritic cells [3].

White blood cells known as lymphocytes proliferate uncontrollably in Hodgkin lymphoma, resulting in enlarged lymph nodes and growths all throughout the body. Two distinct clinicopathologic entities are included in Hodgkin lymphoma (HL): nodular lymphocyte dominated HL (5% of cases) and classical HL (CHL), which accounts for 95% of cases [4]. The worldwide age-standardized incidence rate of Hodgkin lymphoma is 0.98 cases per 100,000 individuals [5]. A literature review, published by Shabbir *et al.* in 2019 on epidemiological features of lymphoma in Pakistan, reported the prevalence of Hodgkin lymphoma as 4.9%, while non-Hodgkin lymphoma is approximately 4.7% prevalent. While in Balochistan, the prevalence of lymphoma cancer is reported to be the highest, i.e., about 9.6% [6].

It was discovered that the Hodgkin lymphoma cell line KM-H2 exhibited both B and dendritic cell phenotypes. Later research revealed that all CHL cases included Reed-Sternberg (RS) cells and RS variants that were positive for fascin, while nodular

lymphocyte-predominant HL's lymphocytic and histiocytic cells tested negative for fascin. These observations have led some researchers to propose fascin as a potential unique marker for RS cells [7].

It might be challenging to differentiate CHL from other forms of lymphomas, even with routine immunohistochemical screening. A small number of RS cells with varying staining intensity have CD20 expression in about 20–50% of CHLs [8]. Only a small percentage of the neoplastic cells may express CD15, and its expression in CHL might be highly variable. Furthermore, some diffuse large B-cell or T-cell lymphomas may test positive for the activation marker CD30, which stains a variable percentage of activated B and T cells [9]. Since the sensitivity of fascin expression for the detection of conventional RS cells is close to 100%, fascin is a sensitive marker for RS cells of CHL even though it is not specific [10].

The absence of fascin demonstrates a strong negative predictive value in ruling out the diagnosis of classical Hodgkin lymphoma (CHL), thus indicating its potential as a differentiating marker between CHL and non-Hodgkin lymphoma. However, there is currently a lack of research on fascin expression specifically in Hodgkin lymphoma within the Pakistani population. Therefore, the rationale of this study was to investigate the frequency of fascin expression in Hodgkin lymphoma among Pakistani population.

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

The study had a cross-sectional descriptive design. The study was carried out at the Diagnostic & Research Laboratory of Liaquat University Hospital, Hyderabad, for a duration of 6 months, i.e., from

Nov/2023 till April/2024. The study enrolled 65 patients with Hodgkin's lymphoma. The sample size of 65 patients was calculated by taking the percentage of expression of fascin in Hodgkin lymphoma as 40% [11], a 10% margin of error, and a 90% confidence interval. A non-probability consecutive sampling technique was used.

Inclusion criteria: The study included known patients diagnosed with Hodgkin lymphoma on the biopsy aged 12 to 60 years, of both genders.

Exclusion criteria: Patients were excluded if they were non-cooperative patients who refused to give consent or participate in the study, patients who had other comorbid blood disorders (as reported by the patients), and patients whose samples were destroyed accidentally or autolyzed during the process.

Expression of fascin was defined on the presence (by detecting fluorescence signal) and intensity of fascin staining through immunohistochemical (IHC) analysis. Using solely cytoplasmic staining, over 10% of the fascin-stained cells of interest were classified as having positive expression of fascin in terms of intensity, while cases with obscuring background staining were excluded¹¹. By doing a biopsy on a suspicious organ or lymph node, HL was definitively diagnosed. It was divided into a number of subtypes. Sclerosis HL (NSHL), Mixed Cellularity HL (MCHL), Lymphocyte-Rich HL (LRHL), and Lymphocyte-Depleted HL (LDHL) were among the subtypes of Hodgkin lymphoma. The Ann Arbor staging system, often known as the Stages of HL, was described as follows:

Stage I: Only one area of a lymph node or one extralymphatic organ had malignancy.

Stage II: One lymph node region and a nearby extralymphatic organ, or two or more lymph node regions on the same side of the diaphragm, were affected by the malignancy.

Stage III: Both sides of the diaphragm's lymph node regions, possibly including the spleen, were affected by the cancer.

Stage IV: One or more organs outside the lymphatic system, such as the liver, bone marrow, or lungs, have been affected by the malignancy.

After obtaining written informed consent, 65 patients in all were included in the study. Regularly prepared tissue specimens that were paraffin-embedded and either formalin- or B5-fixed were obtained from LUMHS's Diagnostic & Research Laboratory. Every tissue was preserved using either B5 fixative or 0% formalin. In all cases under suspicion, a diagnosis was established following standard procedures. These procedures involved morphological examination and/or immunohistochemical analysis. These comprehensive diagnostic approaches ensure a thorough evaluation and accurate determination of the condition. The tissue sections, whether formalin-fixed, paraffin-embedded, or frozen, were deparaffinized if necessary, using xylene or an appropriate deparaffinizing agent, followed by rehydration through a graded ethanol series. Antigen retrieval, if required for formalin-fixed paraffin-embedded sections, was performed by immersing the slides in an antigen retrieval solution and heating them in a microwave or pressure cooker. An appropriate blocking solution was used to block non-specific binding sites. After that, the tissue slices were incubated with a particular primary antibody for fascin that had been diluted in an antibody diluent for an entire night at 4°C. Subsequently, the slides were washed, and a secondary antibody conjugated with a detection system was applied for 1-2 hours at room temperature. After washing away excess secondary antibodies, the target protein was visualized using an appropriate detection system, producing a visible signal. If desired, the tissue sections were counterstained with hematoxylin for

enhanced contrast. The slides then underwent dehydration, clearing, and mounting with a suitable medium. Finally, the distribution and localization of the fascin protein in the tissue sections was examined and analyzed under a microscope, comparing the results to control samples or different experimental conditions throughout the process. Moreover, information regarding the basic biodata along with the socio-demographic details of patients and staging and type of Hodgkin lymphoma was obtained on a pre-designed proforma.

SPSS version 25.00 was used to evaluate all patient data. The frequency and percentage was calculated for expression of Fascin in patients with Hodgkin Lymphoma and also for gender, family monthly income and type of Hodgkin Lymphoma and stage of lymphoma. Normality of the data was assessed via Shapiro-wilk test and as the data was non-normal in distribution so median and interquartile range (IQR) was calculated for age and duration of symptoms. The stratification was done to account for effect modifiers like age, gender, stage and type of lymphoma. Categorical variables were subjected to the post-stratification chi-square test and a p-value of 0.05 was deemed statistically significant.

RESULTS:

A total of 65 patients were enrolled. The median (IQR) age of the patients was 35 (9.5) years. The median (IQR) duration of symptoms was 7 (3.5) years (Table-I).

There were 22 (33.8%) patients of age group 12 to

30 years, 38 (58.5%) patients of age group 31 to 45 years and 5 (7.7%) patients of age group 46 to 60 years. There were 42 (64.6%) males and 23 (35.4%) females. Urban catchment area was reported by 35 (53.8%) patients and rural catchment area was reported by 30 (46.2%) patients. In terms of education status, 12 (18.5%) patients were illiterate, 11 (16.9%) patients had education till primary, 9 (13.8%) patients had done matric, 13 (20%) patients studied till intermediate, 15 (23.1%) patients did bachelors and 5 (7.7%) patients did masters. The monthly income was <25,000 rupees in 9 (13.8%) patients, was 25,000 to 50,000 rupees in 20 (30.8%) patients and >50,000 rupees in 36 (55.4%) patients. With respect to type of HL, NHSL was diagnosed in 49 (75.4%) patients, MCHL was diagnosed in 12 (18.5%) patients, LRHL was diagnosed in 3 (4.6%) patients and LDHL was diagnosed in 1 (1.5%) patients. In terms of stage of HL, stage I was present in 18 (27.7%) patients, stage II was present in 25 (38.5%) patients, stage III was seen in 18 (27.7%) patients and stage IV was present in 4 (6.2%) patients. Expression of fascin occurred in 35 (53.8%) patients of HL (Table-II).

Data was stratified for age, gender, type and stage of HL. It was found that there was significant association between the stage of HL and expression of fascin as indicated by a p value of 0.002. However, none of the other effect modifiers had any significant association with expression of fascin (Table-III).

Table-I: Median (IQR) of Quantitative Variables (n=65)

Variables	Median (IQR)
Age (in years)	35 (9.5)

Duration of symptoms (in months)	7 (3.5)
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Table-II: Frequency of baseline demographic and clinical characteristics (n=65)

Variables	Frequency (percentage)
Age group: 12 to 30 years 31 to 45 years 46 to 60 years	22 (33.8%) 38 (58.5%) 5 (7.7%)
Gender: Male Female	42 (64.6%) 23 (35.4%)
Catchment area: Urban Rural	35 (53.8%) 30 (46.2%)
Educational status: Illiterate Primary Matric Intermediate Bachelors Masters	12 (18.5%) 11 (16.9%) 9 (13.8%) 13 (20%) 15 (23.1%) 5 (7.7%)
Monthly family income: <25000 rupees 25000-50000 rupees >50000 rupees	9 (13.8%) 20 (30.8%) 36 (55.4%)
Type of Hodgkin lymphoma: NHSL MCHL LRHL LDHL	49 (75.4%) 12 (18.5%) 3 (4.6%) 1 (1.5%)
Stage of Hodgkin lymphoma: I II III IV	18 (27.7%) 25 (38.5%) 18 (27.7%) 4 (6.2%)

Expression of Fascin:	
Yes	35 (53.8%)
No	30 (46.2%)

Table-III: Stratification of expression of fascin, with respect to effect modifiers (n=)65

Effect Modifiers	Expression of Fascin		p value
	Yes	No	
Age group:			0.622
12 to 30 years	10 (15.4%)	12 (18.5%)	
30 to 45 years	22 (33.8%)	16 (24.6%)	
46 to 60 years	3 (4.6%)	2 (3.1%)	
Gender:			0.471
Male	24 (36.9%)	18 (27.7%)	
Female	11 (16.9%)	12 (18.5%)	
Stage of Hodgkin lymphoma:			0.002
I	6 (9.2%)	12 (18.5%)	
II	10 (15.4%)	15 (23.1%)	
III	15 (23.1%)	3 (4.6%)	
IV	4 (6.2%)	0 (0%)	
Type of Hodgkin lymphoma:			0.581
NHSL	28 (43.1%)	21 (32.3%)	
MCHL	6 (9.2%)	6 (9.2%)	
LRHL	1 (1.5%)	2 (3.1%)	
LDHL	0 (0%)	1 (1.5%)	

DISCUSSION:

The current study findings revealed that in patients with Hodgkin lymphoma, expression of fascin was seen in 53.8% patients and it was significantly associated with the stage of HL. The majority of the patients in our study were males, of age range 31 to 45 years, in urban catchment areas, majority were educated till bachelors and had a family monthly income of >50,000. The most common type of HL in our study was NHSL and stage II was most frequently encountered.

The cytoskeleton contains the actin cross-linking protein fascin, which is involved in cell motility in a variety of cell types [12]. Cell-matrix and cell-cell interactions have a significant impact on epithelial cell differentiation [13]. These interactions are crucial for the proper organization and stabilization of epithelial cells as well as for keeping the cells in a non-migratory condition [14, 15]. The phenotypic shift to a migratory state, which permits tumor invasion across the basement membrane and

metastasis, leads to the malignant conversion of epithelial cells [16, 17]. This switch is controlled by several actin-binding proteins, including fascin, and necessitates intricate reorganizations of the actin cytoskeleton [18]. Fascin expression in non-neoplastic lymphoid tissue is extremely selective and mostly found in dendritic cells, whereas lymphocytes, plasma cells, and other cells are consistently non-reactive [19]. Nonetheless, in every form of Hodgkin's lymphoma, all or almost all Reed-Sternberg cells and their variations express fascin and exhibit a high level of fascin immunoreactivity [20]. However, little is known about the expression of fascin in our local population with HL. Therefore, the current study was conducted to assess the frequency of fascin expression in HL patients in our local population.

Our study results revealed that expression of fascin was seen in 53.8% patients of HL. Fan et al. revealed that fascin was expressed in 100% of the HL cases [10]. Bakshi et al. similarly revealed 100% expression of fascin in HL cases [12]. Kempf et al. revealed that fascin expression was seen in 60% of the cases of HL [13]. Kim et al. revealed that the neoplastic cells of HL were positive for fascin in 82% of the cases [14]. Studies conducted previously have shown similarly high frequency of fascin as in our study in patients with HL. However, there has been a difference in the rate of positivity in our study and those conducted previously. This difference might be attributed to the level of staining of fascin considered positive for diagnosis of HL, as we only considered those cases which had strong intensity of staining as indicated by IHC score of ≥ 10 used in our study, whereas, previous studies might have used different cut off scores for diagnosing fascin which could have led to differences in the frequency of fascin expression.

Thus, for establishing diagnosis of HL and

differentiating it from other cancers, fascin detection can be a useful tool and thus can help in early detection of HL and help in deciding prompt treatment for such patients.

CONCLUSIONS:

The current study concluded that in patients with HL, fascin was expressed in 53.8% of the patients. Our study findings proposed that fascin is a useful antibody which could help us in establishing accurate diagnosis in patients which are difficult to diagnose and thus can help in deciding optimal treatment for the patients. To validate the results of the current study, larger samples must be used in future research.

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LIMITATIONS:

The study was subject to important limitations. Because this study was conducted at a single center therefore, its findings cannot be broadly applied. Secondly, we did not look for the presence of fascin in non-Hodgkin lymphomas and thus cannot strongly comment that this antibody is solely present in HL patients.

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AUTHOR'S CONTRIBUTION:

Collection and acquisition of data & grammatical corrections

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Concept & design of study & proof read	Dr. Muhammad Rahil Khan
Drafting the article and finalizing the manuscript	Dr. Riyasat Ahmed Memon
Revising critically and make it suitable for final format	Dr. Sooraj Kumar
Acquisition of data and grammatical review	Dr. Gulzar Fatima
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